

Application of Singh-Jha Equation in the Evaluation of b^* Parameter of Laidler-Landskroener Equation in the Hydrolysis of Pyridine Carboxylic Acid Esters

SANJOY KUMAR^a, D. K. VERMA^a, D. P. SINGH^a and L. B. SINGH^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jain College Campus, V. K. S. University, Ara-802 301

^bDepartment of Chemistry, S. P. College, Dumka-814 101

Manuscript received 14 March 1995, revised 10 October 1995, accepted 13 December 1995

Laidler-Landskroener¹ assumed some hypothetical models and applied a complicated mathematical treatment to calculate the size of the active group of activated complex (b^*) for an ion-dipole type of reactions. Singh and Jha² suggested a pair of equation for evaluation of b^* parameter without having any arbitrary assumption which is yet to be tested for consideration. Kumar³ attempted to apply it in the acid-hydrolysis of a single ester benzyl formate. The present authors were attracted towards the study of b^* parameter as it appears very useful and it gives an idea of the size of the active group of the activated complex in such reactions. This according to Elsemogy⁴ is equal to the radius of the active group of the activated complex plus the radius of the water or solvent molecule depending on the mechanism of the reaction. So it is evident that the value of b^* parameter accounts for the solvation of the activated complex and gives an idea about the extent of solvation. Besides, it furnishes a very pertinent information regarding the polarisability of the initial as well as transition state as it is related with molar polarisation energy change $N\Sigma \frac{G e^2}{b^*3}$ reported recently⁵, the positive value of which indicates the initial state being more polarised while its negative value suggests the transition state being more polarised.

Results and Discussion

For the evaluation of b^* parameter the equation of Singh and Jha² is as follows :

$$\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^*} = \frac{1}{A} \left[X - \frac{1 + \alpha}{\alpha} (X + Y) \right] \quad (1)$$

where, X is the product of the slope of the plot $\log k$ vs $1/D$ and temperature, A is $\frac{1}{2.303} \frac{e^2}{2k}$, b_A is the size of the reactant ion, α is half of the dielectric constant of the ester used, k is the Boltzmann constant, e the electron charge, b^* the size of the active group of the activated complex in the reaction and Y is a parameter whose mean value between the temperatures T_1 and T_2 can be determined by equation (2),

$$\log \frac{k_1}{k_2} = \left[\frac{X_1}{D_1 T_1} - \frac{X_2}{D_2 T_2} \right] + Y \left[\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right] \quad (2)$$

Applying these two equations, the size of the active group

of the activated complex (b^*) have been calculated.

The b^* parameter values (Table 1) have been found to decrease with increase in temperature. The decrease in b^* parameter values is logical as the solvation sheath is expected to decrease with the rise of temperature due to increasing randomness in the media. Elsemogy⁴ also determined the size in case of hydrolysis of acetamide in different solvent systems which very well commensurates with what has been reported in Table 1. However, Singh-Jha equation was found not applicable to the hydrolysis of pyridine-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (ethyl nicotinate) in aquo-acetone media as no variation was found in the values of b^* parameter with change in temperature. The constancy in b^* parameter value may be attributed to the mesomeric effect shown due to the different position of the substituent.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF b^* PARAMETER OF LAIDLER-LANDSKROENER EQUATION

Temp.	b^* (Å) value	
	Ethyl picolinate	Ethyl Isonicotinate
298	5.45	5.65
303	5.42	5.48
308	5.36	5.40
318	5.27	5.32

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT VALUES (k , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) FOR ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL PICOLINATE AND ETHYL ISONICOTINATE IN WATER-ACETONE MEDIA

Temp.	Ester	Acetone % (v/v)				
		10	20	30	40	50
298	Ethyl picolinate	17.8	13.2	11.2	10.0	8.5
	Ethyl isonicotinate	20.4	17.0	15.1	13.8	11.8
303	Ethyl picolinate	25.1	18.6	15.9	13.5	11.2
	Ethyl isonicotinate	24.5	21.4	19.1	17.3	15.8
308	Ethyl picolinate	35.5	25.7	21.4	18.2	15.1
	Ethyl isonicotinate	25.7	24.0	21.8	20.3	19.0
318	Ethyl picolinate	70.8	50.1	39.8	33.1	26.3
	Ethyl isonicotinate	30.9	28.8	26.2	24.0	22.8

Experimental

The esters used were of Eldrich make and the organic solvent was purified by standard procedure. The procedure followed for the conductometric measurement was similar to that used by Verma *et al.*⁶. The specific rate constant values for the alkali-catalysed hydrolysis of pyridine carboxylic ethyl esters are shown in Table 2.

References

1. K. J. LAIDLER and P. A. LANDSKROENER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **52**, 200.
2. L. SINGH, R. T. SINGH, R. K. SINGH and R. C. JHA, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 372
3. R. KUMAR, *React., Kinet. Catal. Lett. (USSR)*, 1987, **33**, 229.
4. M. M. ELSEMONGY, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Neue Folge)*, 1975, **94**, 69
5. A. K. SINGH, C. D. SINGH, P. R. PANDEY and D. P. SINGH, 'Proceedings of Convention of Chemists', Indian Chemical Society, 1985, p 37, L. SINGH, V. SHRIVASTAVA, MANJULA KUMARI and R. C. JHA, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 1988, **4**, 53; V. SHRIVASTAVA, R. I. SINGH, S. B. SINGH, P. PRASAD and L. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 619.
6. D. K. VERMA, B. SINGH and R. P. SINGH, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 868.